

Diseases associated with menopause

Katarzyna Szymona-Pałkowska^{1A-G}, Jolanta Adamczuk^{2A-G}, Malwina Cypriańska^{3A-G}, Marta Sapalska^{4A-G}, Agnieszka Pedrycz^{5A-G}, Jacek Kraczkowski^{3A-G}

¹Department of Clinical Psychology, John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin (KUL), Poland

²Private practice, Nałęczów, Poland

³Department of Obstetrics and Pathology of Pregnancy, Medical University of Lublin, Lublin, Poland

⁴The Social Insurance Institution, Lublin, Poland

⁵Department of Histology and Embryology Medical University in Lublin, Poland

Received: January 20. 2017; Accepted: March 10. 2017

Abstract

According to the World Health Organization (World Health Organization, WHO) states that during menopause, in which 12 consecutive months, there has been no menstrual bleeding, without any other reason. However, according to Bręborowicz menopause is a transition period between the reproductive period and old age. During the duration of the gradual extinction of ovarian cycling. It appears last menstrual bleeding. The skin decreases the content of collagen and hyaluronic acid.

This results in a thinning of the epidermis and a decrease in the amount and activity of fibroblasts in the subcutaneous tissue. In perimenopausal increased risk of developing osteoporosis, myocardial infarction, hypertension, atherosclerosis, diabetes and depression.

Keywords: menopause, osteoporosis, myocardial infarction, hypertension, atherosclerosis

Introduction

Menopause is the next stage in a woman's life, located between procreation and the aging of the organism. Associated with the cessation of gonadal function and cessation of menstruation. Changes include the cessation of ovarian synthesis of estrogen and progesterone, and the ongoing transformations translate into the quality of life of women in the field of life biopsychosocial [1, 2, 3].

According to Gonzaga and others [4], by 2030 the number of women who are over age 50 will increase significantly.

According to statistical reports, will increase to 1.2 billion [5]. However, according to McKinney and others [6], life expectancy for women is about 84 years, and the third falls on the postmenopausal period. This makes the quality of life of postmenopausal women is as important as before the onset [7, 8]. It is also believed that this is a matter which still devotes too little attention [9].

Already much has been written about the physiological aspects of menopause and after menopause is not only the changes at the physical level, the numerous changes taking place at the level of mental and social. It is a time very complex and difficult for any woman.

This is the stage of life when in a special way women experience numerous negative stimuli, so paying attention to the time of menopause, both the physical realm and mental is entirely justified.

Normally cycling month is seen by a woman as one of the attributes of femininity. It helps to build a proper self-image. However, this is an image which undergoes constant changes [10].

Menopause is a time when increases the risk of developing disease. To one of these include osteoporosis.

This is a condition defined in accordance with the National Institutes of Health (USA) is a generalized skeletal disease. It characterized by compromised bone strength, which leads to increased fracture risk [11].

According to statistics, currently with the disease affects over 30 million women. This condition should be regarded as one of the leading health problems, because in the first year after the fracture of the hip, the patient's risk of death increases up to 20% [12].

The presence of osteoporosis increases with age. This is a condition of a latent, ongoing in over a decade, in the form of elusive clinically [11].

During the first years after menopause observed a significant decrease in bone mass. It is a phenomenon of a progressive, conditional understated hormonal stimulation, decrease in physical activity and eating disorders [12].

The main reason for the changes in the bones of osteoporosis is a decrease in the concentration of 17-beta estradiol. In the case of estrogen deficiency, an increased release of cytokines osteoblasts, whose role is to stimulate the maturation of osteoclasts (IL-1, TNF, IL-6). At the same time, a decrease of production of the cytokines IL-4, IL-13, IL-18, which are responsible for the increase in bone density [2]. Other risk factors include: a sedentary lifestyle, BMI <19, hip fracture in the mother, the use of glikokortkosteroidów more than three months, the use of anticonvulsant drugs, cytostatics, heparin and smoking cigarettes, drinking alcohol and coffee [13]. Bone strength depends to a large extent on the balance between the processes of resorption and formation. It is also important accumulation of micro-injuries of bones, as well as changes in the micro- and macro-architecture of the bones and the degree of mineralization [14].

Due to the lengthening of the life of the phenomenon of post-menopausal osteoporosis and bone fractures is increasingly common. It is believed that by 2020, the number of patients affected by this disease will increase by 41% [12].

Currently, in order to measure bone mineral density (bone mineral density, BMD), the method absorptiometry double-ray beam (DXA - dual X-ray absorptiometry). The results are compared to the results of the young reference group (T-score) and a group of peers (index Z-score). BMD is given in g / cm^2 . The standard talking in a situation when the T-score ≥ -1.0 SD (standard deviation); osteopenia, when the T-score is -1.0 to -2.5 SD; Osteoporosis, when the T-score ≤ -2.5 SD. To use the BMD of the lumbar spine L1-L4 and proximal femur, according to the World Health Organization [15].

In the case of post-menopausal osteoporosis therapeutic procedure covers lifestyle change, ie. The abandonment of smoking, dietary changes taking into account the increased intake of calcium and vitamin D3 [16].

According Osieleniec et al [11] Additional important defense supplementation, where the daily calcium requirement is in the range of 1200-1500mg and vitamin D3 in a dose of 800-1000 microM / 24h, and in patients at risk (diagnosed with osteoporosis, obesity, malabsorption, reduced exposure to the sun) up to 2000 j.m./24h. The proposed dose of calcium supplementation in the 1500 mg / 24 does not increase the risk of kidney stone formation [17].

While Holick [18] noted that the existing protective creams containing in its composition factor of 8 or higher

contribute to the reduction of skin synthesis of vitamin D up to 97.5%.

In the group of drugs used to treat osteoporosis distinguished bone resorption inhibitors (selective estrogen receptor modulators, bisphosphonates, calcitonin) and substances with a dual mechanism of action (strontium ranelate). It is recommended that the bringing together of these drugs supplemented with calcium and vitamin D [14].

Another condition often experienced by women in menopause is the ischemic myocardium.

According to the literature, coronary heart disease is a complex of symptoms resulting from chronic state of under-supply of heart muscle cells with oxygen and nutrients [19,20].

It is believed that this is a disease that would represent a major clinical problem.

According Stachowiak and others [21] it was a heart attack, stroke and atherosclerosis are the main cause of death among women. Ischemic heart muscle develops in 50% of women and risk increases dramatically after menopause. This is a condition that is the leading cause of death in later life. The development of diseases associated with the aging process of the body, many hormonal and metabolic changes occurring during perimenopause.

Redberg and others [22] have pointed out that women with the clinical course of the disease is often different than men. Pain is uniquely located and may include the area back, jaw, neck or abdominal cavity. Different is the duration of pain, others are also factors that cause it. In women, the main predisposing factors are stress and emotions, not physical, as in the case of men.

Menopause is an important risk factor affecting the cardiovascular system. The observed changes in the circulatory system consist of:

- disorders of lipid metabolism: increase in total cholesterol level, the increase in LDL, VLDL, Lp (a), triglycerides, and a decrease in HDL, which accelerates atherosclerosis [21];
- carbohydrate metabolism disorders in the economy: reduced sensitivity to insulin, the appearance of insulin resistance and hyperinsulinemia, androidal distribution of fatty tissue, the presence of type II diabetes [21];
- impairment of the function of the vascular wall: there is a block calcium channels, an increase in production of endothelin-1, renin, angiotensin II, growth myocyte proliferation, leading to increased vascular resistance, increase blood pressure and atherosclerosis [21];
- adverse shift in coagulation and fibrinolysis: increase of fibrinogen, Lp (a), homocysteine, and TXB2, growth factor VII activity, increase the concentration and ac-

tivity of PAI -1, increased platelet activation, which leads to increased risk of thromboembolic and plaque instability atherosclerosis [21];

According to Sitruk-Ware [19] Estrogen supplementation partially reverses the adverse lipid changes. It was also observed beneficial effects of estrogen supplementation on flow in the arteries. However, in the case of progesterone supplementation, there was a tendency for lowering and raising HDL to LDL. However, James [13] justifies the influence of progesterone on the level of lipoprotein is only marginal. In order to prevent cardiovascular disease, Mosca and others [23] recommend lifestyle changes as well as make a panel of laboratory tests.

Justify that the earlier detection of abnormalities increases the effectiveness of treatment, a fundamental condition for effective action is to implement in the life of certain patterns: increasing physical activity, the use of proper diet, weight loss, smoking cessation.

The decrease of the concentration of LDL cholesterol can be achieved by a reduction in foods saturated fatty acids (butter, lard, fat cheeses, red meat) and the elimination of trans-unsaturated fatty acids, as well as by eating foods fortified with sterols or stanols.

Perimenopausal period in conjunction with abnormal lifestyle contributes to the development of hypertension.

According to the World Health Organization for the upper limit of normal blood pressure is the value of 140 mmHg systolic and 90 mmHg diastolic pressure. Hypertension recognize when the systolic blood pressure exceeds 160mmHg or diastolic blood pressure level exceeds the value of 95mmHg [24].

There are essential hypertension constitute an independent unit of disease and secondary hypertension occurring as a complication of other diseases.

A pressure increase occurs due to an increase in resistance to the peripheral vessels caused by contraction prekapilarów. In contrast, peripheral resistance and heart rate are dependent vascular-motor centers located in the hypothalamus. The pressure regulation is also driven by hormonal and genetic factors [25].

It also stresses the impact of abnormal lifestyle as an element leading to imbalances cortico-subcortical. In this group, you can specify a person performing hard, exhausting work, exposed to chronic stress and high levels of anxiety [25].

Complications associated with hypertensive disease is to increase the pressure of the blood against the walls of the arteries promoting atherosclerosis and threatening attack or stroke.

Hypertension is a disease often diagnosed in women during menopause, and estrogen patomechanism impact on the value of the pressure is very complex.

Estrogens affect the production of angiotensinogen by increasing the activity of the renin - aldosterone also increases the secretion of catecholamines also they have a beneficial effect on the expansion vessels by stimulating the synthesis of prostacyclin [26].

He does not see a direct relationship between hormone replacement therapy and increased blood pressure.

Only transdermal estrogens due to the direct action of vasodilator may lower blood pressure. It is believed that in the group of women with hypertension do not have contraindications to the use of hormone replacement therapy [25].

In the treatment of hypertension used antihypertensive drugs as well as introduces a lifestyle change that is recommended at each stage of hypertension.

According to European guidelines to prevent cardiovascular disease ESH-ESC [24] recommended:

- eating more fruits and vegetables and reduce the intake of saturated fats and cholesterol
- weight loss in obese and overweight
- reduction in the diet of sodium chloride to <1.5g/d
- limiting alcohol consumption to ≤10-20g ethanol per day.

Co-morbidities of hypertension and coronary heart disease escalating significantly during perimenopause it is seen in countries quite often hyperlipidemia.

Atherosclerosis is a metabolic disease of the arteries, a condition that the frequency increases with age.

The main role is played here by fat metabolism disorders and abnormal blood clotting. It involves the formation of small clots perimeter under which occurs rozplem cell membrane of muscle deposition of cholesterol deposits and endothelial damage. Intima of the arteries becomes uneven, loses elasticity and eventually harden. In the coronary, cerebral and renal stenosis occurs. Formed vascular thrombus [24].

Atherosclerosis can have a very varied course depends on the severity of symptoms and organ covered condition.

Most notable of these atherosclerotic lesions in the coronary arteries of heart and cerebral atherosclerosis causes stroke, damage to the focal atherosclerotic dementia.

Risk group of people more likely to increase cholesterol levels in the blood are perimenopausal women. The decline in estrogen levels predisposes to an increase in total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, free fatty acids in the liver, the VLDL fraction and reduce HDL.

Elevated levels of lipids in combination with cigarette smoking, hypertension and an increase in aggregation of platelets may predispose to atherosclerotic plaque [25].

According to Knopp [27] The use of hormone replacement therapy in perimenopausal women contribut-

ed to the decrease LDL by 10-15% and increase HDL by the same amount.

It is also believed that the substitution of 17-beta estradiol in the form of a transdermal reduce serum triglycerides and increase HDL.

However, in studies comparing efficacy of hormone replacement therapy and dietary treatment showed a decrease in triglycerides and LDL by 14% and 19% for HRT and for 3% and 5% of the dietary treatment.

The main objectives of prevention recommended in the prevention of hyperlipidemia:

- avoiding tobacco
- a diet rich in fruits and vegetables
- increased physical activity
- BMI <25 kg / m², to avoid obesity
- systolic blood pressure <140 mm Hg
- total cholesterol <5mmol / l (~ 190mg / dl)
- LDL cholesterol <3mmol / l (~ 115mg / dl)
- glucose on an empty stomach <6mmol / l (~ 110 mg / dL) [24].

According to Roberts [28] in the case of patients with type II diabetes by lowering total cholesterol and LDL can reduce the number of serious cardiovascular complications. Control of lipid metabolism plays an important role in the prevention of cardiovascular disease.

Women in the age of menopause are at increased risk of numerous diseases.

Under the most common symptoms of menopause can hide much more serious disease which is type II diabetes.

Although it is one of the most common diseases of postmenopausal problem is its early diagnosis. It is estimated that the incidence of this disease in women over 50 years of age is around 12% and after the age of 60 has increased to 20% [29].

Considering the causes and the course of isolating the two major forms of diabetes. Type I diabetes, or insulin-dependent diabetes and Type II appearing in the elderly or non insulin dependent diabetes [28].

Type II applies to older people with obesity or other metabolic disorders. Pancreatic insulin secretion in these patients is most often brought sometimes increased. Meanwhile there is reduced sensitivity to insulin. Before the advent of *pełnoobrazowej* diabetes by many years there may be inadequate glucose tolerance giving no more clinical symptoms [30].

Typical symptoms are an increased level of glucose in the blood. There is glycosuria and polyuria amounting to several liters of urine a day causes an increase in thirst and dry mucous membranes. Undiagnosed or poorly treated can result in coma glycemica [28].

Type II diabetes treated with diet and medication. Restrictions apply energy. Reduced fat and simple carbohy-

drates, recommends vegetables, fruits and polysaccharides [29].

Type II diabetes, hypertension and dyslipidemia contribute to the development of cardiovascular diseases. There has been a change in metabolism, which, together with obesity, smoking, nicotine and less active lifestyle will accelerate the development of atherosclerosis [28].

Another condition implicated in the turbulent changes in the woman's body at this time is depression.

According Bręborowicz [2] depressive disorders during the climacteric are diagnosed in about 50% of women presenting to a doctor because of somatic complaints arising from the period of menopause.

The emergence or worsening of depressive symptoms at this time, is not only associated with fluctuations in the concentrations of estrogen levels but also with changes in the area of family life, social and professional. This is also the time when it comes to changes in the perception of their own femininity and evaluation of one's own body. During this time may occur relapses or exacerbations, also the co-exists with bipolar disorder.

It is estimated that the prevalence of depressive disorders aged 45-55 stands at 30% among women 35-44 years of 5.8%, while in the group of women who are perimenopausal 55% [31].

According Santoro et al [32], there are several factors that increase the likelihood that time depressive disorders. These include history of depression, stressful life experiences, insomnia, lack of social support, cigarette smoking, elevated BMI, younger age, as well as belonging to African-Americans. In contrast, Geerlings and others [33] argue that depression may be an early symptom promising future cognitive decline.

As research in the development of depression during menopause also play a hormonal factors, genetic and psychosocial [34,35].

It is believed that the tendency to depression are influenced by changes in hormonal levels. Estrogen deficiency reduces the concentration and activity of neurotransmitters such as serotonin and catecholamines, causing a decrease in the drive and mood. There is also no stimulation of estrogen receptors within the limbic system responsible for the regulation of emotional behavior (eg. Contentment) [2].

In contrast, Sprawka [31] reports that the duration of menopause has an effect on the incidence and severity of depression and anxiety but not the main cause.

As defined by the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders major depressive episode is defined as the presence of 5 or more of the following symptoms persist for most of the day nearly every day for at least two consecutive weeks.

At least one of the symptoms must be depressed mood or loss of interest or experience pleasure [32].

With the diagnosis of depression is based on:

- depressed mood,
- loss of interest or pleasure of feeling on all forms of activity, or most of them,
- excessive sleepiness or insomnia,
- psychomotor retardation or agitation,
- a significant decrease or increase in body weight,
- decrease or increase in appetite.
- fatigue or decrease in energy,
- impaired concentration, thinking,
- the problem of decision-making,
- thoughts about their worthlessness,
- inadequate or excessive guilt,
- recurrent thoughts of death,
- thoughts or suicide attempts [32, p.14].

The diagnosis of perimenopausal depression is based on carefully gathered psychiatric interview and further treatment conducted in collaboration with a gynecologist.

Often the cause of the difficulty in identifying depressive disorders may be their unusual character.

Depressed mood and fatigue psychomotor drive is then not the dominant symptom. This leads to, "masking" by somatic symptoms.

The most common mask of depression such as sleep disorders. Waking too early, rarely somnolence. The continuing anxiety, back pain, headache, trigeminal neuralgia, chest pain resembling angina, disorders of the gastrointestinal tract [32].

Research shows that the use of premenopausal hormone replacement therapy helps to improve cognitive function. The quality of verbal memory HRT following the onset of menopausal symptoms was significantly higher compared to women who started treatment with HRT after menopause [36].

According to research the use of HRT reduces the severity of hot flashes, improves the quality of sleep, alleviate depressive symptoms [33].

All women during perimenopause is recommended modifying current eating habits, conduct regulated lifestyle with an emphasis on sleep hygiene and physical activity tailored to the individual abilities of each of the women.

Taking care of a healthy lifestyle as well as performing preventive testing will be the basis of maintaining good health, attractive appearance, and thus improve the quality of life in all its aspects.

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Correspondence address

Jacek Kraczkowski
jacek.kraczkowski@tlen.pl

Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.